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NPS CORNER

Using amberNPS to predict lethal blood concentrations of NPS

VIBE CODING

Now is the best time to start

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Everything you need to know

So what's stopping you from vibe coding? NOW IS THE BEST TIME TO START

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Last week, I cleaned up my mom's Yahoo Mail and removed duplicate downloads using vibe-coded Python scripts [1,2]. What would normally take hours of manually downloading attachments and deleting duplicates, or accomplishing through sketchy third-party tools, turned into a quick, automated task. The alternative was to surrender and pay for extra storage.

This experience inspired me to ask my fellow forensic scientists: what's holding you back from vibe coding? If you haven't started yet, now's the perfect time. Large language models (LLMs) are improving considerably.

Interestingly, I didn't start learning Python because of that Yahoo Mail problem; it was the other way around. I started exploring Python because I saw how useful it could be in my work, particularly in automating repetitive tasks and making sense of complex outputs. Applying it to something as simple as email cleanup just reinforced how powerful and transferable those skills are.

For many of us, coding wasn't exactly a core skill growing up. Literally my only prior exposure to coding was during the era of Friendster. Back then, we felt like absolute hackers just changing our profile background and auto-playing music through rudimentary HTML. I did have a coding class in college, but it was more for compliance. Our thinking back then was that we weren't computer science majors anyway.

Today, vibe coding has made programming feel accessible in a way that would have seemed impossible before. You just need a problem worth solving, a clear description of what you want, and enough patience to refine the output. And there is a particular kind of fulfillment when a script runs successfully, doing exactly what you want it to. It is especially rewarding when the solution came from an idea you translated into a prompt and refined through conversation with an LLM. It feels less like programming in the traditional sense and more like

solving a practical puzzle with immediate results.

I have been applying the same approach to laboratory tasks. The most memorable Python scripts I've vibe coded so far are automating repetitive data handling, parsing libraries like SWGDRUG [3] into individual CSVs for comparative mass-spectrum visualization (samples shown in Figure 1), generating entire chromatograms from raw files and 3D interactive plots, separating extracted spectra from bloated AMDIS report (*.FIN) files, and building a retention-time-binning workflow for our massive raw GC-FID datasets.

These kinds of applications highlight where vibe coding becomes especially valuable in forensic science. Many of our workflows involve repetitive, structured processes, which are ideal candidates for automation, yet they are often done manually or with limited software flexibility. Vibe coding opens up opportunities for better data exploration. Instead of being constrained by vendor software interfaces, we can try to build custom queries, filter results based on case-specific criteria, or integrate outputs across multiple instruments. Even small improvements in these areas can save significant time and reduce cognitive load during analysis.

Of course, the convenience comes with a warning: do not get too cocky or careless. LLMs can generate code that looks polished and convincing but contains subtle logic errors or makes wrong assumptions for your use case. **Never upload sensitive data** (case files, client information, or proprietary lab data) to public LLMs. This is why responsible AI use matters. Our AI Task Force Report [4] emphasizes the importance of human review, validation, domain oversight, and data security, because in forensic work the cost of trusting unchecked code or exposing confidential information can be far greater than a failed script. The point is not to outsource judgment but to sharpen it.

TABLE 1: PRACTICAL TIPS FOR WORKING WITH LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS TO IMPROVE CODE GENERATION

Tip	Why It Works
Claude first-try superiority	Often produces solid code on first attempt
Prompt chaining	Ask one LLM to build your prompt then feed to another to bypass token limits
Context first	Upload/paste file-format samples upfront to lead LLM to the right path
Code explanations	Ask LLM to break down scripts line-by-line when you forget what they do
Path management	Right-click target folder or file and click "Copy as path"; early identification saves time
Start small	Single tasks first (parse files, check Unicode compatibility) then build up
VS Code for beginners	Incredibly user friendly even for non-programmers
Okay to be (cautiously) lazy	Let LLM describe your rows/columns/values
Don't be afraid to ask!	No question is too noob. Token limits? Many reliable LLMs are available.

Over time, I've picked up a few practical strategies that make vibe coding more effective.

One thing I noticed early on is that not all LLMs perform the same. I was initially hesitant to use Claude mainly because it does not offer a free tier, but I've come to admit that it often gives solid code on the first attempt. However, it is known for its not-so-generous token limits. As a work around, I sometimes ask another LLM to construct a well-structured prompt first and then paste that into Claude. This prompt-chaining approach often improves output quality while avoiding truncation issues.

Context also makes a big difference. When working with structured data like chromatograms, peak tables, or AMDIS output, I provide a sample of the file format upfront, especially when using token-generous models. This helps the model understand exactly what it is dealing with and reduces ambiguity.

Another useful habit is asking the model to explain the code it produces. Whenever I revisit a script I haven't used in a while and doesn't have proper documentation, I simply ask an LLM to break it down. This turns every script into a learning opportunity and gradually builds deeper understanding. Path management is also critical. Identifying file paths early in the process will save significant time. Right-click your target folder and "copy as path" to get it exactly right from the start.

It also helps to think in small steps. Start with a single task like parsing a file, extracting peak areas, renaming outputs, and then build from there. It's okay to be lazy as long as you're cautious. If you don't feel like describing your complex data (what the rows, columns, and values are), just upload an excerpt of it in TXT/CSV or image format and ask the LLM to "parse" or describe it first. This is actually the right way to start most of the time because you're ensuring the LLM understands your data before you begin your long conversation. Don't be afraid to ask! When I was starting with VS Code (which I found incredibly beginner-friendly), I asked the simplest questions like "what is a Terminal and where is it?" and uploaded a screenshot of the entire VS Code window. If token limits worry you, many reliable LLMs are at your disposal. Many of my current tools, from automation scripts to AMDIS helpers and 3D interactive-plotting utilities, began as simple snippets that evolved over time.

FIGURE 1. MASS SPECTRA GENERATED FROM THE SWGDRUG LIBRARY PARSER FOR EPIANDROSTERONE AND 2,5-DIMETHOXYPHENYLNITROTYRENE, SHOWING THE ANNOTATED TOP IONS AND NORMALIZED RELATIVE ABUNDANCES ACROSS THE M/Z RANGE.

We are now in an era where coding is no longer a barrier. The real skill now is articulating exactly what you want the computer to solve. If like me Friendster HTML was your coding peak, imagine what you could build today. Your next lab automation breakthrough is waiting in a simple prompt.

The only thing stopping you? The first click. Vibe code responsibly. Vibe code boldly. **Just start.**

References:

- [1] Barbo NMA. Yahoo Mail Attachment Bulk Downloader v1.0.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19642374> (accessed 18 April 2026).
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- [3] Barbo NMA. SWGDRUG Library Parser v1.0.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19642257> (accessed 18 April 2026).
- [4] Trobbiani S, Devincenzi T, Barbo NMA, Shapiro AM, Mardal M. Task Force Report - on Integrating Artificial Intelligence into Forensic Toxicology. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18997665> (accessed 18 April 2026).

AI Generated image a scientist coding in the laboratory - Copilot, Microsoft

